

IMPORTANCE OF LANGUAGE TEACHING APPLICATIONS IN INCREASING STUDENTS' VOCABULARY DURING FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Sobirova Zarnigor Rakhimovna

Associate Professor, PhD, Bukhara State University,

Tursunova Sitorabonu Uktamovna,

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Faculty of Foreign Languages, English
language and literature, 2nd year graduate student

Abstract. It is no secret that in today's globalized world, learning foreign languages increases the importance of personnel training. Learning new words, which is one of the main factors in learning a foreign language, has an incomparable place. This article details the importance of language learning apps in improving students' vocabulary during foreign language learning.

Keywords: foreign language, mobile applications, language skills, language courses, student psychology, etc.

The four basic language skills, listening, reading, speaking and writing, are integral to language learning. For successful and effective learning and teaching in foreign language courses, it is necessary to develop and strengthen these four basic language skills according to the learning level and needs. The problem is not to determine the position of the four basic skills in foreign language teaching or to question its definition, but to show how these four basic skills are approached and mastered by students. When students hear and understand foreign language lessons correctly, they will be more successful and prepared if they can speak correctly and effectively. Especially in today's modern science, the issue of effective learning of foreign languages and easier assimilation of new vocabulary has been researched by

several scientists, but it has always been an urgent issue. In today's world globalization, it is natural that such an approach to this issue is necessary. Often, the organization of a bilingual education system in learning a foreign language makes it possible to study several foreign languages in depth. Sometimes, the number of hours of lessons and special textbooks allocated to learning foreign languages is not enough to master the lesson, which can cause problems in learning foreign languages perfectly. Modern information and communication technologies (ICT) and online resources on the Internet play an important role in finding a solution to these problems.

In increasing students' interest in lessons, ICT and Internet resources can be a factor that increases educational effectiveness, including motivation to learn a language. The ability of the teacher to create his own electronic educational resources with the help of information and communication technologies is of great importance in the development of this field. It should be noted that if a student knows his mother tongue well, has the ability to follow the rules of the language, his existing linguistic experience can create a foundation for mastering another foreign language. It also helps to master the grammatical concepts and terms of the language faster. In this way, he learns the similarities and differences between languages and learns another foreign language easily. Comparison of language phenomena at the phonetic, lexical, and grammatical levels will be material that enriches the field of linguistics. Therefore, cross-linguistic comparative analysis is important. This ensures not only the acquisition of new material in a foreign language, but also the students' approach to it with special interest. If a student knows the rules and basic concepts of one language well, he is confident that he can learn another language. Application of innovative and new pedagogical technologies to foreign language education - orientation of the person according to the requirements of the society, organization of education based on these requirements, and formation of the person as a mature staff in all respects based on the principles, methods and relevance of education, his creates favorable conditions for full manifestation and development of abilities and opportunities. Another distinctive

feature of innovative pedagogical technologies is the priority of the teacher's activity, the fact that the student is the main figure in the educational process. In the educational process, the correct formation of knowledge, lexical, grammatical and pronunciation concepts, the correct content of the knowledge system, self-control skills in the minds of students are components of innovative pedagogical technologies. Currently, the most effective teaching methods and teaching methods that are guaranteed to achieve the goals set by teachers and pedagogues in the educational process not only form students' independent thinking, free decision-making skills, but also help them solve problems and such teaching methods are the most advanced feature of pedagogical technology. The famous German scientist Y.V. As von Goethe said: "Whoever does not know a foreign language does not know his own language." For this reason, not only foreign language specialists, but also all future personnel studying in other higher educational institutions that do not specialize in languages, learning foreign languages and forming a free exchange of ideas in them is considered one of the most important tasks. There is no doubt that one of the main requirements for personnel today is excellent knowledge of foreign languages. It is important to ensure the priority of the education system in the processes of personnel training in all fields, including the introduction of new technology-mechanisms for teaching foreign languages. The goals of teaching a foreign language are determined based on the demands of society, social orders, conditions, and policies. The goals of foreign language teaching depend on the progress and development of society. Before starting to teach a foreign language in higher education institutions, all foreign language teachers must define it in advance and introduce new methods of teaching it to students.

In today's fast-paced world, information and communication technologies are also growing rapidly. The XXI century is an era of high technologies, our youth is moving not only in the spirit of the times, but also in line with the development of the electronic world. Therefore, if someone wants to learn a foreign language, he can use not only the lessons in the educational institution, but also mobile applications aimed at learning

foreign languages more easily and effectively. It is known that at present no one lives without the use of the latest mobile devices. Everyone will have free time. Focusing on learning English, one of the international languages, will no doubt help you learn about the world in the future. The following is a list of mobile apps for learning English:

- LinguaLeo. The biggest advantage of this app is that it is organized in the form of a game to learn English. As you play the games, you will move on to new levels, enriching your personal vocabulary. In addition, LinguaLeo has a lot of materials, works, videos, songs.

- Duolingo. It's a completely free English learning app, and it's a great ad-free app. Learning English in this application is also a game, you will not be bored and the process of learning the language will be fun. You go through stages, you score points, and if you make a mistake, you lose points.

- Memrise. Another great app. The application is based on the method of memorizing 44 words per hour. The main tool of the application are memes. These memes allow you to remember a large number of words through images. In addition, the application contains a variety of audio and video materials.

- The AnkiDroid app provides flashcards as a convenient way to learn and memorize new words. There are 6,000 ready-made cards in the application database. You can create them yourself. Cards are one of the best ways to remember.

- FluentU. One of the best ways to learn English is through English-language media content. He has a lot of movies, videos, audios, reality shows. You will watch these videos with interest and at the same time develop your English language and pronunciation

In short, in order for our talented young people to become experts in their fields of interest, they must first and foremost be fluent in a foreign language, including English. Therefore, the introduction of technologies, ensuring that teaching methods meet the requirements of the times are the urgent tasks of pedagogical scientists. We also think that students who want to work on themselves and are interested in learning

a foreign language perfectly will be able to shoot two rabbits with one bullet if they use the above mentioned mobile apps in their free time. At a time when the economic, political, cultural and educational ties of our country with the world are growing, the interest of our youth in the life, culture, traditions and language of foreign countries is growing. The role of foreign languages, especially English, in the development of these relations is invaluable. It can be said that a new stage, a new era in the teaching of foreign languages has begun in our country. The demand for learning a foreign language is also growing day by day. Knowledge of a foreign language is required in every field, whether it is business or politics. As mentioned above, the role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in improving the quality and effectiveness of education, the targeted organization of games in the form of games that interest students is very important. In fact, the scope of their application is expanding day by day, and technical means are becoming an integral part of the learning process. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technology is one of the most effective methods. And as well, interactive teaching is instructing the pupils in a way they are actively involved with their learning process. The professor of John's university Rita Dunn said: "If the child is not learning the way you are teaching, then you must teach in the way the child learns".

Today, learning a foreign language requires a spiritual and educational approach to organize each lesson on a unique, unrepeatable level based on the modern educational system and national heritage. The need to provide the educational process with modern pedagogical technologies is one of the conditions for the implementation of the "National Personnel Training Program". To provide young people studying in all educational institutions of our republic: pre-school educational institutions, general secondary schools, vocational colleges, academic lyceums and higher education institutions with modern pedagogical and information technologies, with a new knowledge system continuous organization of armaments is the demand of the times. The role of advanced technologies is very important for the student to express his

opinion freely, to explain the topic in a group or team. Therefore, the goals and objectives of teaching a foreign language and its methodology should be in line with and meet the requirements of the interests of our society and the state, as well as the requirements of the young generation. Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Naturally, learning the language of a foreign country brings many difficulties. However, in spite of them, today the youth of Uzbekistan are looking at foreign languages with great interest and enthusiasm. Innovative technologies are factors that increase the effectiveness of education. For example, through methods such as "Brainstorming" and "Pinboard", we can see that the level of students and the interest in learning a foreign language is increasing. "Brainstorming" method is a method designed to test the knowledge levels of students. With this method, the teacher organizes a question-and-answer session to focus students' attention on the subject of the lesson. In this process, the questions should be related to the topic in a different, logical, interesting or scientific-political way. This question-and-answer session can take 5-10 minutes, depending on the activity of students and young people. Using the "Brainstorming" method, students search for answers to various questions, use all possibilities to get out of problematic situations, and look for ways to get out of the situation. This leads to an increase in their interest in the lesson and a new topic, and to their activation. When using this method, each student's answer is taken into account. The main thing is that each student is asked to justify and defend his answer. In order to improve the effectiveness of the lesson, the most recommended method is the method known as "Pinboard". The word "Pinboard" is derived from English and means "pin-strengthening", "board-board". The main essence and purpose of this teaching method is that the discussion and educational conversation with the participation of students is directly connected with the practical method.

Thanks to the large-scale reforms implemented in the education system in our country, incomparable opportunities and conditions have been created for the younger

generation to acquire modern knowledge and grow up as a perfect person. In today's conditions, training of highly qualified personnel should be carried out on the basis of current systems and modern pedagogical technologies. Advanced and modern pedagogical technologies serve as a guaranteed tool for achieving the goal and show their positive results. In fact, 80% of the successful organization of each lesson depends on the correct development, organization and implementation of the educational process. Each student develops a culture of communication and discussion. The ability to express one's opinion fluently and freely appears, logical thinking skills develop. The ability to express one's personal and worldly thoughts is formed when one goes to the blackboard or in front of many people. Skills such as being able to listen to one's peers, taking his opinion into account, sticking to one's own opinion, and proving another's wrong answer will appear. In conclusion, it should be said that teaching a modern language is aimed at forming a more cultured person, who has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. This ensures that teachers can familiarize themselves with the most advanced approaches and then integrate them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Sufficient attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in the course of training aimed at teaching a foreign language. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct organization of the training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then will students be able to think independently and develop an interest in language learning.

References:

1. Mirolyubov A.A., Raxmanov I.V., Setlin V.S. *Taxriri ostida. O'rta maktabda chet tillar o'qitishning umumiy metodikasi.* - T O'qituvchi 1974
2. Tursunov I.Y. *Xalq pedagogikasing dolzarb muammolari.* – T.: “O'qituvchi”, 1990.

3. Oxford L.L. Language learning strategies: What Every Teacher should know. – N.Y. New Bury House Publishers 1990
4. ies.ccsenet.org International Education Studies Vol. 11, No. 7; 2018, 178
5. İngiliz Dili Bölümlerinde Uygulanışı (Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi). Atatürk Üniversitesi/Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İngiliz Dili Ve Edebiyatı Anabilim Dalı, Erzurum. Barın, M. (2002). Yabancı Dil Öğretiminde Dinleme Becerisinin Önemi. Atatürk Üniversitesi Journal of Social Sciences, 2(28-29), 17-22.